

SmartCHP
COGENERATING A RENEWABLE FUTURE

D.4.2

Report on the Control model

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

This deliverable first presents integration of the dynamic models of the SmartCHP components into a predictive system model. The model is parameterized and partially validated using measurements from a turbocharged four-cylinder diesel engine and a swirl burner both running on fast pyrolysis bio-oil. The system model then is used for design and evaluation of controllers both on plant level and component level. Control design on plant level is about finding an operation plan for electricity and heat generation in response to predicted energy demand profiles. The operation plan is then translated into some reference or setpoints for the component-level components to track. Model-based control strategies are formulated, and predictive simulations illustrate their performance.

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Symbols

symbol	description	unit
p	pressure	[Pascal, Bar]
T	temperature	[K]
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate	[Kg/s]
η	efficiency	[-]
c_p	specific heat at constant pressure	[J/kg/K]
c_v	specific heat at constant volume	[J/kg/K]
P	power	[J/s] [watts]
M	Torque or molar mass	[N.m] [kg/mol]
$R = c_p - c_v$	Specific gas constant	[J/kg/K]
ω	Rotational speed	[rad/s]
$k = c_p / c_v$	Ratio of specific heats	[-]
H_l	Lower heating value	[J/kg]
V	volume	[m ³]
λ	Air/fuel ratio, oxidizer/fuel ratio	[-]
\dot{Q}	Heat transfer rate, heat loss rate	[J/s]
m	mass	[kg]
δ_0	stoichiometric air/fuel ratio	[-]
x, y	Weight/Molar fraction	[%]

Subscripts

subscript	description	subscript	description
c	Compressor	b	Boiler
e	Engine	OC	oxidation catalytic converter
eg, g	Exhaust gas, flue gas	DPF	diesel particulate filter
t	Turbine	SCR	selective catalytic reduction
tc	Turbocharger	OCH	oxidation converter housing
IR	Intake receiver	PM	Particle matter
OR	Outlet or exhaust receiver	US	Urea solution
β	Cylinder input	inj	Injected
ϕ or f	fuel	NH3	Ammonia
amb	ambient	SCR	Selective catalytic converter
a	air	th	Thermal
w	Water	Gen	Generated
TES	Thermal energy storage	SOC	State of charge

1. Introduction

1.1 Motivation

The purpose of the SmartCHP project is to develop highly flexible, cost competitive, FPBO-fuelled CHP units providing heat and power in the small-scale range and potentially also cooling. Using FPBO as fuels enables the use of highly efficient diesel engines, and by introducing a smart control the optimal performance is achieved over a very wide range of heat & power, which result in reduced OPEX and CAPEX.

SmartCHP aims at a highly flexible cogeneration unit which means the plant can adjust heat generation between a minimum and maximum level at all the engine electrical loads (heat/electricity ratio between 2 and 10). To exploit such flexibility, a smart control unit is needed. Developing a dynamic system model is the first step toward such control unit. The dynamic model enables design and evaluation of the controllers both at components level and at the system level. Various operating points at different operating modes and scenarios can be evaluated with the dynamic model, to find optimal working conditions. The smart control unit ensures an energy production plan with maximum response to the fluctuating energy demands, maximum fuel efficiency, and minimum level of pollutants emission. Finally, the predictive system model integrated with smart control unit is a useful tool to predict demand response, components utilization rates, and their energy efficiencies when the plant generates energy for a certain use case of cogeneration (e.g., hospitals, commercial buildings, green houses, etc). These parameters are inputs for financial and feasibility study of SmartCHP technology before its large-scale roll-out. This deliverable document the system model, control model and predictive simulation of the integrated system/control model.

1.2 Brief process description

The technical concept of the cogeneration plant is presented in Figure 1.1. Heat and power generation are combined in a hybrid system of diesel generator and flue gas boiler. One unique and new feature of this plant is that it is fueled with fast pyrolysis bio-oil (FPBO) originating from different types of biomasses.

The input air is heated before entering diesel engine through a heat exchanger that recovers heat from diesel engine flue gas. FPBO is combusted in diesel generator to generate heat and power. Heat is extracted from the engine jacket and carried by engine coolant through a heat exchanger. The flue gas burner/boiler uses solely the oxygen content of engine flue gas to combust FPBO. Depending on heat and power demand profiles either only CHP engine is operating or both engine and burner are on. When power demand is high and heat demand is low, there is no need to generate extra heat and only the diesel generator will be operating, and the burner will be off. If heat demand is high and power load is low, heat from CHP engine might not be enough to cover heat demand therefore extra heat will be generated by the burner/boiler. The hybrid system of diesel generator and flue gas boiler provides a flexible heat-to-power ratio. In this sense, the plant is a flexible

cogeneration unit that can deal with the fluctuating energy demand and varying availability of wind/solar power.

The plant also includes a newly designed flue gas cleaning system, which is placed downstream of the boiler. It includes oxidation catalyst (OC) which reduces carbon monoxide (CO) and unburned hydrocarbons (HC), diesel particulate filter (DPF) which reduces particulate matter (PM), and CO and HC, if any, and selective catalytic reduction (SCR) with urea for NOx reduction. Urea solution is injected upstream of SCR into the flue gas stream. Heat is extracted from the cleaned flue gas by heat exchangers or condensation units. In the project, a prototype of such plant is under development.

Figure 1.1: SmartCHP concept

1.3 Control model elements

Table 1 explains the elements of the control model. More details of the elements follow in the next sections.

Table 1. Description of control model elements

Element	Sub-element/description
Objective	Develop a smart control unit to ensure safe operation, maximize demand response, maximum fuel efficiency and keeps emission in the limits.
Exogenous variables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ambient temperature and pressures, 25 °C and one atmosphere, respectively, water input temperature is also 25 °C • Air flow preheating temperatures, input air temperature to engine is 160 °C • Control set-points, constant engine speed of 1500 RPM, air ratio between 1.05-1.4 for boiler burner, NOx emissions below 200 ppm
User heat and power profile	Hourly heat and power demands in [kW]
Control design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Components-level controls including engine rotational speed control, air-ratio control of burner, NOx emission controller that regulates ammonia injection in SCR • Optimal operational planning: plant-level controls, operating modes including power-led, heat-led, or economy mode.
Energy efficiencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engine electrical efficiency, ratio of generated power to primary fuel energy • CHP engine thermal efficiency, ratio of generated heat from engine to its primary fuel energy • Boiler fuel efficiency, ratio of generated heat to primary fuel energy • Plant energy efficiency, ratio of total generated heat and power to total primary fuel energy
Demand response	Fulfilled and unfulfilled demands, plant energy outputs compared with energy demands
Level of emissions	CO, NOx, HC emissions, downstream of the cleaning system, discharged to the environment

2. System model

The cogeneration system consists of a diesel generator, a flue gas boiler, a dedicated flue gas cleaning system, and heat exchanger and condensers. The focus here is on the flue gas path and simulating the behavior of system components that are most affected by the biofuel properties and the resulting flue gas characteristics i.e., its temperature and its content. Figure 2.1 shows system configuration that reflects this

focus point. In the figure, state variables of the components are indicated. The diesel generator represented only by diesel engine components on the flue gas path, includes fresh air heating, compressor, intake receiver, cylinders, outlet receiver, and turbine. It is noted that engine rotational speed is the parameter describing engine and alternator interface and is present in the system model. An adaptive PI controller regulates the FPBO injection to keep the engine speed constant at 1500 RPM.

The next component is the flue gas boiler with a burner running on FPBO and using the remaining engine flue gas oxygen as oxidizer. The interface between the burner and diesel engine is the tail pipe R4, which is modelled as a reservoir element and allows for modelling the backpressure by the burner or by the cleaning system in the case engine flue gas is directed to the cleaning system and the boiler is by-passed. Included in the boiler model, is a hot water heat exchanger.

The flue gas from the boiler finds its way to the cleaning system. The first component is OC that may affect NO₂/NO_x ratio. After OC, DPF is placed that might cause significant backpressure due to accumulation of PM inside it. This backpressure is modelled by the reservoir component R7 that is placed between OC and DPF. The last component in the cleaning system is SCR unit, which consists of a hydrolysis part where the injected urea solution vaporizes and forms a flow of NH₃, and SCR cells where NO_x is reduced by the NH₃ absorbed on the surface of SCR catalyst. Last, a condensation unit downstream of the cleaning system is placed to absorb heat from flue gas. The system model also includes the dynamics of fuel injection devices in the engine and burner, and urea solution injection device in the SCR unit.

An outline of the plant simulation model procedure follows as:

- Develop dynamic models on component level, this includes models of turbo-charged diesel engine, water heating boiler, OC, DPF, SCR, reservoirs, injectors and measuring sensors.
- Fine-tune and validate component models, this is to identify set of parameters that minimize the difference between model outputs and measurements. Experimental data and literature data are used.
- Define interfaces between components and identify their models, important interfaces are engine-boiler interface characterized by temperature, flow rate and mixture of engine flue gas, and boiler-cleaning system interface, characterized by flue gas's temperature, pressure, and its pollutants content
- Integrate all model components into system model,
- Verify and validate system model, this task aims at comparison of model simulations with measurements from a prototype of the integrated system

Figure 2.1: SmartCHP system configuration, components, and their interfaces

1.1 Parameter tuning

As SmartCHP plant is under construction and experimental validation of its model is not possible at this stage, data from individual components are the basis to tune their parameters. For parameter tuning, we have formulated non-linear regression models to minimize error between predictions by the model and the available experimental data.

The parameters of diesel engine model are tuned with respect to steady state measurements of compressor mass flow, flue gas oxygen, turbo pressure, and after-turbine flue gas temperature from an experimental diesel engine running on FPBO blend with methanol [1]. For more on the experimental set-up refer to [2]. The engine runs at different load steps (4-17-27-37 kW_e) with constant engine speed 1500 rpm. Figure 2.2 compares engine measurements with model predictions.

Figure 2.2. Comparison of engine measurements and model prediction; (a) flue gas temperature raising around cylinder, (b) oxygen content of engine flue gas

Data from an experimental setup of burner/boiler running on FPBO with artificial engine flue gas as oxidizer [3] is used to parameterize the model of NO_x emissions from burner/boiler. In the experiments, input flow to the burner is a mixture of air, nitrogen, and carbon dioxide. The oxygen content of inflow mixture and its temperature is adjusted by regulating mixture percentages and preheating of the mixture, respectively. Figure 2.3 compares measurements of burner NO_x emission with the model predictions. Oxygen content varies between 15-19 % and inflow temperature between 200-450 °C.

Figure 2.3: Comparison of model prediction with experimental data, NO_x emissions from burner for different oxygen content of flue gas; square hollow markers show experimental data and circle filled markers show model data, the colors show different flue gas input temperatures

For DPF backpressure model the data in [4] is used where experimental measurements of exhaust gas volume flow rates, particulate mass and inlet exhaust temperatures are available. For parameter tuning of OC model and estimation of its effect on NO/NO₂ ratio, the data both in [5] and [6] is used. In the experiments, an OC unit is mounted for aftertreatment of exhaust gas from a diesel, 4-stroke, 4-cylinders engine. The experimental setup was equipped with a non-dispersive ultraviolet analyser to measure nitric oxide (NO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) separately.

The data used for SCR parameter tuning is from Kwak et al. [7], where model Cu/zeolite catalysts were experimentally investigated and their corresponding NO_x reduction performance at different SCR temperatures were recorded. Figure 2.4 compares NO_x reduction performance by the SCR model and those reported by Kwak et al. [7]. The mean absolute percentage error is 5.9%. The figure also shows NH₃ reduction percentages predicted by the model.

(b)

Figure 2.4: Comparison of model prediction with experimental data, NO_x reduction by SCR at different SCR temperatures

1.2 Steady-state model of SmartCHP

In this section, first, a steady-state model of SmartCHP plant is derived. This is done based on the system model presented in Section 2. It will be shown how power and heat generation are non-linearly coupled in the SmartCHP concept. This dependence between heat and power is an important input for operation planning of the plant.

A simple way to present engine operation is to model its efficiency and air/fuel ratio as a function of torque generation. This simplification helps derive a simple model of the entire plant where heat generation can be formulated as a function of engine load.

Engine efficiency and engine air/fuel ratio are logarithmic functions of engine load:

$$\eta_e = a_{\eta_{e,1}} \log(Pe) + a_{\eta_{e,2}} \quad (1)$$

$$\lambda_e = a_{\lambda_e,1} \log(Pe) + a_{\lambda_e,1} \quad (2)$$

In which ai are constant coefficients

Then, the steady-state flue gas mass flow out of the engine is

$$\dot{m}_{geout} = \dot{m}_{\beta e} + \dot{m}_{\phi e} \quad (3)$$

Where $\dot{m}_{\beta e}$ is mass flow of fresh air input to engine and $\dot{m}_{\phi e}$ is the mass flow of engine fuel (FPBO).

The mass flow of engine fuel is related to its efficiency and power generation by

$$\dot{m}_{\phi e} = \frac{P_e}{\eta_e H_l} \quad (4)$$

Substituting η_e from Equation (1) into Equation (4) gives

$$\dot{m}_{\phi e} = \frac{P_e/H_l}{a_{\eta_e,1} \log(Pe) + a_{\eta_e,2}} \quad (5)$$

Engine air/fuel ratio is defined as

$$\lambda_e = \frac{\dot{m}_{\beta e}}{\dot{m}_{\phi e} \delta_0} \quad (6)$$

As $\dot{m}_{\phi e} \delta_0$ is the amount of air needed for complete stoichiometric combustion of fuel mass flow \dot{m}_{ϕ} , where δ_0 is the stoichiometric air-to-fuel ratio.

The amount of fresh air in the engine exhaust gas is $\dot{m}_{\beta e} - \dot{m}_{\phi e}$, and with 23% weight percentage of oxygen in fresh air (assuming molar oxygen content of fresh air is 21%), the mass flow of oxygen in the engine flue gas is

$$\dot{m}_{O_2,eout} = \dot{m}_{\beta e} - \dot{m}_{\phi e} \delta_0 = \dot{m}_{\phi e} \delta_0 (\lambda_e - 1) * 0.23 \quad (7)$$

In the SmartCHP concept, the boiler burner is operating solely on the oxygen content of engine flue gas, i.e., $\dot{m}_{O_2,eout}$. Therefore, for a predetermined oxidizer/fuel ratio, the fuel mass flow that can be injected into the burner/boiler is

$$\dot{m}_{\phi b} = \frac{\dot{m}_{O_2,eout}}{\lambda_b \delta_{0b}} \quad (8)$$

In which λ_b is oxidizer/fuel ratio in the burner and δ_{0b} is the stoichiometric oxygen-to-fuel ratio.

The heat generated from boiler is

$$\dot{Q}_{gen} = \dot{m}_{\phi b} H_l = \frac{\dot{m}_{O_2,eout}}{\lambda_b \delta_{0b}} H_l \quad (9)$$

To improve FPBO combustion, the input air to the engine is heated. The corresponding heat flux input to the engine is

$$\dot{Q}_{air,heating} = c_p \dot{m}_{\beta e} (T_{a,in} - T_{amb}) \quad (10)$$

The heat input by engine flue gas into boiler is

$$\dot{Q}_{in} = k_{cool} \left(\frac{1 - \eta_e}{\eta_e} P_e + \dot{Q}_{air,heating} \right) \quad (11)$$

In which k_{cool} indicates how much of the available heat flux is carried by the exhaust gas. The coolant removes the remaining heat flux. The coefficient k_{cool} is parameterized as

$$k_{cool} = a_{0,cool} - a_{1,cool} e^{a_{2,cool} * M_e}$$

where $a_{0:2,cool}$ are constant coefficients, and M_e is engine torque. At the steady-state operation, engine torque $M_e = \frac{P_e}{\omega_{e,ref}}$ and $\omega_{e,ref} = 1500$ rpm.

Useful flue gas heat from boiler and CHP engine reads

$$\dot{Q}_{u,fluegas} = (\dot{Q}_{gen} + \dot{Q}_{in})(1 - \eta_{loss})\eta_{th,g} \quad (12)$$

where $\eta_{th,g}$ is thermal efficiency of heat recovery from exhaust gas, and η_{loss} is heat loss from boiler burner box and combustion chamber.

Useful heat recovered by the engine coolant is

$$\dot{Q}_{u,coolant} = (1 - k_{cool}) \left(\frac{1 - \eta_e}{\eta_e} P_e + \dot{Q}_{air,heating} \right) \eta_{th,c} \quad (13)$$

where $\eta_{th,c}$ is thermal efficiency of heat recovery by the engine coolant.

Total useful heat is

$$\dot{Q}_u = \dot{Q}_{u,fluegas} + \dot{Q}_{u,coolant} - \dot{Q}_{air,heating} \quad (14)$$

Equation (14) assumes the heat used for input air heating is recovered from engine flue gas. It represents total useful heat from SmartCHP as a function of two parameters engine load (P_e) and boiler oxidizer/fuel ratio λ_b . This is a useful way to present system output when designing plant wide control.

Similar to the formulations for useful heat, energy efficiency can be derived as a function of operating variables P_e and λ_b .

For the fuel energy input to the engine, the aggregated energy efficiency reads

$$\eta_{plant,e} = \eta_e + (1 - k_{cool})(1 - \eta_e)\eta_{th,c} + k_{cool}(1 - \eta_e)(1 - \eta_{loss})\eta_{th,g} \quad (15)$$

The energy efficiency term $\eta_{plant,e}$ represents the aggregated energy efficiency of CHP engine which includes efficiency of power generation, efficiency of heat recovery by the engine coolant and efficiency of heat recovery from flue gas after the boiler. This efficiency corresponds to fuel energy input to the engine which is $\frac{P}{\eta_e}$.

For the air heating energy input to the engine, the aggregated energy efficiency reads

$$\eta_{plant,air} = (1 - k_{cool})\eta_{th,c} + k_{cool}(1 - \eta_{loss})\eta_{th,g} \quad (16)$$

The energy efficiency term $\eta_{plant,air}$ represents the aggregated energy efficiency of CHP engine corresponding to the input energy for air heating ($\dot{Q}_{air,heating}$). This includes efficiency of heat recovery by coolant and efficiency of heat recovery from flue gas after the boiler.

For the fuel energy input to the boiler, the aggregated energy efficiency reads

$$\eta_{plant,b} = (1 - \eta_{loss})\eta_{th,g} \quad (17)$$

The energy efficiency term $\eta_{plant,b}$ is the efficiency of heat recovery after the boiler. This efficiency corresponds to fuel energy input to the boiler which is \dot{Q}_{gen} .

Then the aggregated efficiency of SmartCHP plant can be calculated as a weighted average of the efficiency terms:

$$\eta_{plant} = \frac{\frac{P}{\eta_e}}{\frac{P}{\eta_e} + \dot{Q}_{air,heating} + \dot{Q}_{gen}} \eta_{plant,e} + \frac{\dot{Q}_{air,heating}}{\frac{P}{\eta_e} + \dot{Q}_{air,heating} + \dot{Q}_{gen}} \eta_{plant,air} + \frac{\dot{Q}_{gen}}{\frac{P}{\eta_e} + \dot{Q}_{air,heating} + \dot{Q}_{gen}} \eta_{plant,b} \quad (18)$$

Heat generation from boiler can be controlled by adjusting boiler oxidizer-to-fuel ratio (λ_b) in a feasible range e.g., 1.05-1.4 where minimum $\lambda_b = 1.05$ gives maximum boiler heat generation. Another way to regulate heat generation by the boiler is bypassing engine flue gas directly to the cleaning system without passing through burner. In this case, the fraction of oxygen content of engine flue gas which is used in the boiler burner is regulated by a bypass control.

Figure 2.5: shows total useful heat generation as a function of engine power. Every point in the blue highlighted area is a possibility for power/heat generation and

annotated with plant efficiency when operating at that point. The upper line limiting the blue area corresponds to the case when $\lambda_b = 1.05$, meaning that all the oxygen content in the engine flue gas is used for FPBO combustion in the burner. The bottom border line corresponds to the case when burner is off, and all the heat is generated only by the CHP engine. Or all the engine flue gas is bypassed. Please note that the results in Figure 2.5: are based on the identified model from BTG data coming from 4C engine running on FPBO. Further, the following assumptions are made:

- thermal efficiency of heat recovery from engine cylinder by the coolant $\eta_{th,c} = 60\%$
- thermal loss from the boiler combustion chamber and burner box is η_{loss} is 2%
- thermal efficiency of heat recovery from exhaust gas downstream of SCR $\eta_{th,g}$ is 95%

Figure 2.5 suggests that heat and power generation will not be completely decoupled in the SmartCHP concept. For a 50kWe engine, at engine load around 25 kW, maximum heat generation becomes possible. This plot shows that the feasible operation region area of the SmartCHP system is considerably larger (i.e., more than 100%) than that of the CHP engine. Hence, there exists a certain degree of freedom for heat generation at all the engine operating points, which can be exploited for optimization when plant is operated in heat-led mode.

In Figure 2.5, as engine load increases, more heat becomes available through engine jacket and its flue gas heat recovery. When engine load decreases, the temperature of its flue gas drops but its oxygen content increases. This allows boiler to bear more heat load thereby maintaining the response to high heat demands. This way of operation, the plant offers a wide range of heat-to-power ratio.

Figure 2.5: Heat generation and plant efficiency as a function of engine power

3. Control model

The dynamic system model is used for development of smart control unit which consists of two types of control design at two different levels:

- Optimal operational planning – plant level - finding optimal operating points for use cases of SmartCHP (hospitals, commercial buildings, etc)
- Advanced control design – component level – actuations to follow set points

A basic design concept of SmartCHP smart control unit is presented in Figure 3.1. When the optimal operating points are specified by the operational planning module, they will be translated into some set points for component controllers.

The focused controls are:

- Engine speed,
- Boiler Air/fuel ratio
- SCR NOx reduction by urea injection
- Heat management (flue gas flow and water flow in boiler, heat exchangers, condenser)

Figure 3.1: a basic design concept of SmartCHP smart control unit

The integrating principle for control design at component level is that the estimations and measurements from upstream components are used by

downstream controllers. For example, the mass flow, temperature, and oxygen content of engine flue gas is used by the boiler control to regulate air ratio and outflow temperature. The design of preliminary controls on component level is addressed in Deliverable D3.4.

Here the focus is on the plant wide control and optimal operational planning. Figure 3.2 shows the interactions within the optimal operational planning module i.e., of the optimization layer with the other layers. In the system identification layer, the parameters of the system model are tuned, and the steady state model presented in section 1.2 is identified. This simplified steady state model together with the energy demands and price forecasts input to the optimization layer to find optimal working points. An operating mode will govern the optimization problem formulation.

Some of the more common operating modes of micro-CHPs are power-led, heat-led, or economy mode. In a power-led mode, there is one degree of freedom, and that is to follow the power demand profile. In a heat-led mode, priority is given to fulfilling the heat demand. As it is shown by Figure 2.5, SmartCHP has a non-linear coupling of power and heat generation. Therefore, an optimization problem needs to be formulated to first follow the heat demand then with the remaining degree of freedom, either to follow power demand or to minimize emissions or maximize efficiencies. In an economy mode, priority is given to cost minimization, and profit maximization, minimum emissions, or maximum efficiency. Neither heat demand nor power demand will completely be followed. Problem formulations for heat-led and economy modes and their solution methods follow in the next sections.

Figure 3.2: Optimization layer interactions

1.1 Problem formulation for optimal operational planning

3.1.1 Basic concept

A basic concept for optimal operational planning and smart control of SmartCHP is presented in Figure 3.3. The concept consists of three blocks: load forecast, operational planning, and system model. Load forecast includes models of electrical and heating demand, and for possible use cases of SmartCHP system, i.e., hospitals. Optimal operational planning determines those operating points that maximizes some objective function, subject to operational constraints. These generated operating points serve as set points for the controllers on component level. The system model evaluates the alternative operational planning and feedbacks to the operational planning block system cost, profit, emissions, and fulfilment of the demands. Note that the performance of controllers is influential on system performance in terms of generated power, emissions, and respecting operational rules.

Figure 3.3: a basic concept of optimal operation and smart control of SmartCHP

3.1.2 Load forecast

In order to assess the net incomes of a CHP plant in the future, one day ahead forecasts for loads (electrical and heating) are used to determine day-ahead prices for the electricity market. They are also used to study the response of CHP hardware and software components to sudden and abrupt changes in the demand profile. The purpose of the SmartCHP project is to develop highly flexible, cost competitive, FPBO-fuelled CHP units providing heat and power and potentially also cooling. Therefore, forecast of these energy carriers are the starting point for operational planning.

3.1.3 Optimal operational planning for SmartCHP

The formulation of the operational planning problems includes defining the decision variables (Operating point variables), objective function (optimization criteria), and constraints. In the following a general description of these aspects applicable for SmartCHP is presented.

3.1.3.1 *Operating point variables*

Engine

- rotational speed
- generated torque (= generated power divided by rotational speed)
- temperature of input air (heating before compressor)

Note that for a constant engine rotational speed, the operating point of the engine could be presented by engine generated power.

Boiler

- oxidizer/fuel ratio (air ratio)
- on/off burner
- flue gas input temperature (assuming a heat exchanger between engine and burner)
- generated heat from boiler heat exchanger (water input flow rate)

Cleaning system

- flue gas input temperature
- NOx reduction performance

There is interdependence between operating points of different components. For example, assuming a constant air ratio for burner, the operating point of the engine (speed, generated torque) will determine the operating point of the boiler (generated heat). Or NOx reduction performance is a function of SCR temperature which will be affected by flue gas input temperature to the cleaning system.

3.1.3.2 *Objective function*

Depending on the mode of operation, the objective function for operational planning could be formulated differently. For power-led mode, the primary objective is to fulfill all the electricity demand at all times. For heat-led mode, the primary objective is to fulfill heat demand and then to optimize operation for maximum fuel efficiency and minimum pollutants emissions. For economy mode, Operational costs including profit and fuel efficiency is the main objective function. Parameters are electricity price, heating price, FPBO price, maintenance costs, price penalties due to unmet demands and emission penalties due to exceeding predefined limits.

3.1.3.3 *Constraints*

Operational and safety rules:

- Boiler burner should be off when oxygen content of flue gas is low, i.e., engine flue gas oxygen < 8%
- The intermittent operation of burner/boiler must be ensured, or the emitted pollutants can be quite high
- Burner can start up again after some minutes from the last shut down
- Engine coolant temperature must stay in a predefined safe interval
- One stop per day should be forced for cleaning
- Maximum two stops per day is allowed, otherwise wear and degradation of plant components can be quite high
-

Environmental rules:

- NO_x, PM, CO, and HC emissions must remain below a certain limit

3.1.3.4 Solution methods

In order to solve the formulated operational planning problem, a solution method is employed. The choice of solution method depends on the type of problem formulation. Mixed integer programming, dynamic programming, and reinforcement learning methods are the possible choices. Mixed integer programming and dynamic programming are preferred solution methods when energy demands, and prices could be predicted with an acceptable accuracy. This makes the problem in hand a deterministic problem to solve, as the input parameters to the optimization problem are less uncertain. On the other hand, when a reliable prediction of energy demands and prices are not available, then the problem in hand will be of an uncertain type. This could be due to uncertain contribution of renewable sources like wind and solar on the supply side or changing consumption behavior on the demand side. In the uncertain case, stochastic online optimization methods like reinforcement learning are preferred.

3.1.4 Prediction by system model

Once an alternative for operational variables is specified, the system model evaluates this alternative and calculates the objective functions (cost, profit, emissions) corresponding to the alternative. Included in the system model are the design of various controllers which has a significant effect on system performance in transient operations. The performance of the controllers in each operation mode can be evaluated via predictive simulations.

1.2 Smart control design structure

SmartCHP control unit at the highest level should specify the optimal operating points of the engine, specified by engine load, and the operating point of the boiler specified by its air ratio, in response to fluctuating electricity and heat demands. The reference trajectories for these two operational variables are generated either by an offline trajectory generator or by an online trajectory generator. The offline

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_{e,min} \leq P_e(t) \leq P_{e,max} & \quad \forall t = 1, 2, \dots, T \\
 \lambda_{b,min}^{ref} \leq \lambda_b^{ref}(t) \leq \lambda_{b,max}^{ref} & \quad \forall t = 1, 2, \dots, T
 \end{aligned}$$

In the problem formulation (19), expressions $\dot{Q}_u(P_e, \lambda_b^{ref})$ and $\eta_{plant}(P_e, \lambda_b^{ref})$ imply that heat generation and plant efficiency are functions of engine power and boiler air ratio. This formulation ensures that heat demand is fulfilled. Plant efficiency remain above 85% all the time, the operational variables $P_e(t)$ and $\lambda_b^{ref}(t)$ must stay within allowed/feasible limits, and the maximum number of start-stop allowed is 2, with a minimum of one start-stop for cleaning. The objective cost function to minimize is the unmet demand of electricity plus fuel efficiency lost due to start-stops. The cost of fuel efficiency is expressed in equivalent quantity of unmet demand. For example, the cost of each start-stop can be considered to be equivalent to loss of 2kW of useful energy i.e., $c_{on/off} = 2$.

3.3.1 Dynamic programming solution method

The problem formulation in (19) is a nonlinear, non-convex mixed integer problem which is very expensive to solve. Therefore, dynamic programming is used as the solution method which basically divides the original problem into smaller problems which are easy to solve.

Dynamic programming is used to solve the problem of optimal operational planning when it is expressed as a Markov decision process (MDP). A Markov decision process is introduced by three elements: stage, state, and decisions (actions). We structure the operational planning problem into multiple stages. Each stage is a time step for which the operating plan should be determined i.e., every 15 minutes, every hour, every day, etc. The Markov state of the SmartCHP operation dynamics is given by

$$s = (Q_{TES}, s_{onf}, n_{onf}) \quad (20)$$

In which Q_{TES} is the remaining heat in the thermal energy storage (TES) or the state of charge of TES. Although, the state variable Q_{TES} is a continuous variable, in the dynamic programming formulation it is sufficiently finely discretized i.e., $Q_{TES} = \{0, 1, \dots, Q_{max}\}$. Q_{max} is the maximum capacity of TES. The state variable s_{onf} is the state of plant's on/off operation. It is a binary variable with one indicating that the plant is running, and zero when plant is off. The state variable n_{onf} is the number of stops that the plant has experienced since the start of planning period until current time. When the maximum number of stops allowed during the planning period is $n_{onf,max}$, then $n_{onf} = 0, 1, \dots, n_{onf,max}$

Actions $x = (P_e, \lambda_b^{ref})$ are legal operating points of the engine and the boiler/burner, with $x = (P_e, \lambda_b^{ref}) > (0, 0)$ meaning the plant is running and $x = (P_e, \lambda_b^{ref}) > (0, -)$ means the plant is off. Acting x_t when system state is s_t will transit the state to $s_{t+1} = f(s_t, x_t)$ in the next planning period. State-state transitions read

$$Q_{TES}(t+1) = Q_{TES}(t) + [\dot{Q}_u(t) - \dot{Q}_u^d(t)] * T_s \quad (21)$$

Where T_s is the time duration of a single time step.

$$s_{onf}(t+1) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } P_e(t) = 0 \\ 1 & \text{if } P_e(t) > 0 \end{cases} \quad \forall t = 1, 2, \dots, T \quad (22)$$

$$n_{onf}(t+1) = \begin{cases} n_{onf}(t) + 1 & \text{if } s_{onf}(t) = 1 \text{ and } P_e(t) = 0 \\ n_{onf}(t) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

The updated system state is $s_{t+1} = (Q_{TES}(t+1), s_{onf}(t+1), n_{onf}(t+1))$.

Transition cost incurred in each time step reads

$$g(s_t, x_t) = C_{el} + C_Q + C_\emptyset + I_{onf} * C_{onf} \quad (24)$$

For optimization, only variable costs are relevant and considered in the cost function. The first term is the cost of electricity demand fulfillment and reads

$$C_{el} = \max \{0, P_e^d(t) - P_e(t)\} \quad (25)$$

Which implies that there will be cost associated with electricity production when it falls short than the demand. In the case of extra power generation, no cost is calculated. The assumption is that extra electricity could be sold to the smart grid. It is noted that this cost function is formulated so that the original idea of SmartCHP is supported which is SmartCHP should provide full electricity demand when other renewable sources are not available.

The second term C_Q is the cost of TES and heat demand fulfillment, the third term C_\emptyset is the cost of FPBO, and C_{onf} is the cost of one stop/start if planned which is indicated by indicator variable I_{onf} .

SmartCHP in each planning period (dynamic programming stage) can either provide the full demand for heat, or has shortage of heat supply, or produce excess heat i.e., the unused heat to remain in the storage exceeds the maximum capacity of TES. Formally, when at time period t , shortage of supply happens, that means $Q_{TES}(t) < 0$. When excess heat is produced, that means $Q_{TES}(t) > Q_{TES,max}$. When all heat demand is fulfilled without shortage nor excess heat, that means $0 < Q_{TES}(t) < Q_{TES,max}$. Accordingly, the term C_Q can read

$$C_Q = \begin{cases} -\min(0, Q_{TES}(t)) & \text{if } Q_{TES}(t) < 0 \\ \max(0, Q_{TES}(t) - Q_{TES,max}) & \text{if } Q_{TES}(t) > Q_{TES,max} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

The cost of FPBO C_\emptyset associated with the operating point $x = (P_e, \lambda_b^{ref})$ is

$$C_{\phi}(x) = \frac{(P_e(t) + \dot{Q}_u(t)) * T_s}{\eta_{plant}(x)} \left(1 - \frac{\eta_{plant}(x)}{0.85}\right) \quad (27)$$

in which $\eta_{plant}(x)$ indicates plant energy efficiency at the operating point x . It is noted that $C_{\phi}(x)$ is the cost of extra FPBO than the case when plant efficiency is 85%. When $\eta_{plant}(x) = 0.85$, $C_{\phi}(x)$ is zero meaning that no extra cost is considered for this operating point, as it satisfies the target efficiency $\geq 85\%$. When $\eta_{plant}(x) < 0.85$, $C_{\phi}(x)$ becomes positive, imposing the cost of extra fuel caused by lack of efficiency. This also can be seen as a transformation of the efficiency constraint in the formulation (19). Conversely, when $\eta_{plant}(x) > 0.85$, $C_{\phi}(x)$ becomes a negative cost which relates to the fuel saving associated with the operating point x .

Optionally, there can be a final cost $g(s_N, x_N) = v_Q Q_{TES}(t)$ representing, e.g., the value of the heat remaining in the TES and v_Q is the value per kWh of heat.

We can now solve this problem using Bellman's principle of optimality. For the general problem, our objective is to minimize the sum of cost functions over all stages of the decision process. Let us define the optimal final cost as

$$G_N(s_N) := g(s_N, x_N)$$

and the optimal cost when we are at stage k as

$$G_k(s_k) := \min_{x_k} \{g(s_k, x_k) + G_{k+1}(s_{k+1})\} \quad (28)$$

With this the optimal operating points at each time step is given by

$$x_k^*(s_k) := \operatorname{argmin} \{g(s_k, x_k) + G_{k+1}(s_{k+1})\} \quad (29)$$

Note that the procedure to solve for optimal solution $x_k^*(s_k)$ starts from the last time step and continues backward until all stage optimal solutions are calculated.

There are significant advantages when approaching SmartCHP operational planning problem with dynamic programming (DP). Firstly, the effect of thermal storage and its maximum capacity can easily be considered. Secondly, the computational speed of DP solution method allows for solving operational planning on an extended planning horizon of 24 hours, 48 hours, or even one week. For DP, the computational time increases linearly with the planning horizon. Please note that for the case of mixed integer programming, computational effort increases exponentially with the planning horizon. Thirdly, the DP offers a flexible cost function so that the operational preferences of SmartCHP can readily be incorporated into the planning task.

4. Control model results

In this section, the results of model-based control designs at both plant level as well as at the component level is presented and the response of SmartCHP plant to

fluctuating electricity and heat demand is predicted. To make the model results more sensible, the electricity and heat demand profiles are based on promising use cases of SmartCHP (e.g., hospitals, school buildings) in connection with market assessment [8].

The problem formulation reflects a heat-led operating mode as illustrated in (19). The primary driving parameters in simulations are electrical load on the modified diesel engine and the air ratio in the burner/boiler. Simulations will show at which hours the heat from CHP engine is not enough to respond to the heat demand thereby extra heat should be generated by the boiler. Conversely, there will be times when the heat from CHP engine exceeds heat demand thereby boiler should be off. It should be noted that for the sake of a reasonable simulation run time, we adjust system time constants so that every hour shrinks to 200s of simulation time.

Flexibility, low emission and maintaining high fuel efficiency at all the power levels are the motivations for SmartCHP. Therefore, here in this section predictive simulations show the results of heat-to-power ratio, energy production, energy efficiencies, and NO_x emissions. Moreover, the performance of the controllers is evaluated. Formation of NO_x and performance of SCR in reducing this pollutant is depicted. Dynamics of pressure, temperature, mass flow, and oxygen content of flue gas at different sections of the plant are also shown.

1.1 Case study: SmartCHP generates for a school building

Figure 4.1 shows electricity and heat demand profiles for a school building in a typical day in winter. Electricity demand peaks at 15 kW around 7-8 am. Heat demand is high during the night and drops to 45kW around noon. In this Figure, the results of operational planning are also depicted.

Figure 4.1: Heat-led operational planning in response to electricity and heat demand profile of the use case, $Q_{max} = 20kWh$

The energy generation plan in Figure 4.1 meets all the heat needed but it does not fully follow electricity demand profile. This is mainly because during the day hours, the demand for electricity is high while demand for heat is low. Generating more electricity would cause more extra heat generation for which there would be no demand. Nonetheless, the calculated energy production plan still give rise to some extra heat. The extra heat generation can be seen in Figure 4.2 which shows the state of charge (SOC) of the thermal energy storage together with the SOC mismatch between heat demand and heat production. Positive values of SOC mismatch show that extra heat i.e., more than maximum capacity of TES has been generated and wasted. For example, up to hour 13, an accumulated amount of 80kWh of heat energy has been wasted. On the other hand, at hour 14, a shortage of heat happens because at this hour the plant is off for cleaning. This mismatch could be seen as a direct influence of low TES capacity which is 20kWh.

Figure 4.2: State of charge of the TES in response to electricity and heat demand profile of the use case, $Q_{max} = 20kWh$

To show the effect of TES capacity on operation plan, TES capacity increased from 20kWh to 60kWh, and the results are shown in Figure 4.3 and Figure 4.4. In this scenario, two on/off operation are planned, at time 8am and 13pm. No shortage of heat is incurred, and maximum extra heat wasted is 10kWh.

Figure 4.3: Heat-led operational planning in response to electricity and heat demand profile of the use case, $Q_{max} = 60kWh$

Figure 4.4: State of charge of the TES in response to electricity and heat demand profile of the use case, $Q_{max} = 60kWh$

Figure 4.5 shows the performance of the component-level controllers. Engine governor design allows for satisfactory constant speed control. The burner oxidizer-to-fuel ratio controller is a feedforward type that uses estimates of engine flue gas temperature and composition (mass flow and oxygen content) to regulate fuel injection. At high engine transient, this controller reaction may fall behind engine flue gas changes. Nevertheless, this controller shows a good performance in reference

tracking. The inverse of oxidizer-to-fuel ratio (i.e., fuel ratio) is depicted in this figure and it relates to the percentage level of utilization of full available capacity of the burner.

Figure 4.5: Component level control, engine rotational speed and burner oxidizer-to-fuel ratio control

Energy efficiencies are presented in Figure 4.6. Efficiency analysis can be performed by utilizing energy or exergy concepts [9]. Here the focus is on energy efficiencies. They are calculated as ratio of output useful energy to input energy of FPBO. FPBO has a low heating value (LHV) of 16.9 MJ/kg[10].

The efficiency of electricity generation can increase to 33 % at full load but at low engine load, fuel efficiency of electricity generation is low. Simulations show that the plant can maintain overall fuel efficiency of at least 80 % at both low and high engine loads. Please note that energy efficiency at engine transients might hit high efficiencies more than 98 %. This is because of large heat capacity of boiler heat exchanger that can, for a short while, keep providing heat energy even though the input fuel energy to the boiler or the engine changes. It is noted that a final efficiency analysis of SmartCHP plant is possible when realistic thermal efficiencies of heat recovery are estimated from data coming from SmartCHP prototype.

Figure 4.6: Energy efficiencies for heat-led response to electricity and heat demand profile of the use case, $Q_{max} = 60kWh$

Figure 4.7 shows the spatial evolution of flue gas pressure. Normally, the pressure decreases as the flue gas goes through boiler and find its way through cleaning system. Every part of the cleaning system acts as a flow restriction and might have a contribution to pressure drop. Diesel particulate filter, due to accumulation of soot, is a component causing a significant portion of this pressure drop.

(b)

Figure 4.7: flue gas pressure at different plant sections when water heating in the boiler consumes 55 % of the flue gas heat

When engine load increases/decreases, its oxygen content increases/decreases (Figure 4.8). Mass flow rate is also almost proportional to engine load (Figure 4.9). The increment of boiler mass flow out with respect to engine mass flow out is the extra FPBO injected into burner. The mass of urea solution injected upstream of SCR is the difference between boiler and SCR outflows. The response of the flue gas boiler to the change in the oxygen content depends also on heat demand. When there is enough oxygen and extra heat is needed, boiler will use the available oxygen to generate more heat, otherwise it remains off.

Figure 4.8: oxygen content flue gas at different plant sections for heat-led response

Figure 4.9: flue gas mass flow rate gas at different plant sections for heat-led response

Formation of NO_x in the engine flue gas and boiler flue gas are shown in Figure 4.10. Most of the NO_x is due to engine operation while boiler has a minor contribution. At high engine loads as well as transients, NO_x formation can reach above 1500 ppm.

Figure 4.10: NO_x formation for heat-led response to electricity and heat demand profile of the use case

The evolution of flue gas temperature at different sections of the plant is shown in Figure 4.7. The main assumption is that in the boiler heat exchanger, 40% of flue gas heat is consumed for water heating, the rest goes to the cleaning system. This number can be adjusted by sizing the tubes inside boiler heat exchanger.

From the heat-led response, the electrical load remains between 4-13kW, and the temperature of flue gas at engine exhaust (p3eng) and tailpipe reservoir R4 (before entering boiler burner) increases from 150 to 200 °C. However, flue gas temperature at boiler exhaust pipe can reach 570 °C as at some hours the boiler operates 90% of maximum capacity which results in generating 80-100 kW of thermal energy and about 45% of that heat goes into SCR unit. This situation could be harmful for the cleaning system. As a remedy, the boiler heat exchanger can be designed so as it absorbs 70% of the flue gas heat for water heating and letting less thermal energy into the cleaning system. The temperature of flue gas for this case is shown in Figure 4.12. As seen, the temperature of SCR remains in the safe interval 200-400 °C.

Figure 4.11: Flue gas temperature at different plant sections when water heating in the boiler consumes 55 % of the flue gas heat

Figure 4.12: Flue gas temperature at different plant sections when water heating in the boiler consumes 70 % of the flue gas heat

The performance of SCR NO_x reduction with a feed-forward controller is illustrated in Figure 4.13 (a) and (b) for two cases when boiler heat exchanger removes 70% and 55% of the flue gas heat. A step change in the estimated NO_x excites the controller to increase urea injection. NO_x reduction performance depends also on SCR converter temperature. To show the effect of SCR temperature on NO_x reduction, two scenarios are considered. In the first scenario, shown in Figure 4.13 (a), 70 % of flue gas heat is consumed for boiler water heating. As a result, the SCR temperature stay between

200-400 °C. In this scenario, the controller can keep NO_x emission low (below 300 ppm) in steady state operation, but in fast transients and start-ups, there is a peak in NO_x leak downstream SCR.

It is noted that the SCR model is tuned with literature data published. Further controller design optimization will be pursued when experimental data from the developed cleaning system of SmartCHP become available.

In the second scenario, shown in Figure 4.13 (b), 55 % of flue gas heat is consumed for boiler water heating which leads to higher SCR temperatures (above 600 °C). Generally, the performance of NO_x reduction is severely degraded because of a cool or very hot converter. The degraded performance of SCR in cool temperatures below 230 °C is in agreement with data published in the literature, e.g., see also Figure 2.4. On the other hand, it is important to keep the temperature of the converter below 550 °C or thermal aging and severe degradation can happen because of excessive heat. The conclusion here is that the SmartCHP control unit needs to adjust the temperature of input flue gas to the SCR unit to ensure maximum NO_x reduction and its safe operation. The actuations needed for regulating the temperature is placing an adjustable heat exchanger upstream the cleaning system to remove excessive heat from input flue gas. This normally can be addressed in the design phase of boiler heat exchanger. Nonetheless, such cool or very hot SCR situation must be avoided during normal plant operation to keep emissions in the limits.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.13: NOx reduction performance; water heating in the boiler consumes (a) 70 %, (b) 55 % of the flue gas heat

5. Conclusion

In this document, a dynamic system model of SmartCHP cogeneration plant was used to design and evaluate controllers both on component level and plant level. The design of controllers on plant level entails solving an optimization problem to obtain optimal operating points for the components, in response to fluctuating electricity and heat demands. A general formulation for the operational planning problem was presented and an efficient solution method namely dynamic programming was devised. The performance of the designed controllers is illustrated through predictive simulations. The results confirm that the operational planning module in heat-led mode enables SmartCHP unit to supply nearly all the heat demand and a part of power demand while minimizing the cost for energy supply. The results also show that there are design parameters that affect the performance of smart control unit. Heat management before entering the cleaning system by placing an optimized heat exchanger upstream the cleaning system is crucial for safe and efficient operation of the SCR unit. Boiler burner operating point was defined as an adjustable control input to the plant. This means the thermal power of the boiler can be regulated either by bypassing a part of engine flue gas directly to the cleaning system or by adjusting air ratio for the burner.

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